

ISic0656

I.Sicily inscription 0656

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Centuripae

Place of origin (modern)

Centuripe

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Centuripe, Museo Archeologico Regionale di Centuripe, inventory KA846 + KA861

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Q(uinto) · Pompeio Sex(ti) · f(ilio) ·
2. Quir(ina) (vac.undefi) Pri[s]çø
3. Sosiu[s] [Pr]iscus pa[truo]

Apparatus

Text after Eck 1996 / AE 1996.790 and controlled against photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493946

EDCS 3700329

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 1996.0790

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1993.0829

Libertini, G 1926. Centuripe. Catania. At 45

Libertini, G 1953. Centuripe. Nuove indagini sulle costruzioni presso il Mulino Barbagallo. Campagna di scavo 1950-51. *Notizie degli Scavi di Antichità.* 353-368. At 356

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica.* 51: 161-196. At 168 fig.33-34

Eck, W. 1996. Senatorische familien der kaiserzeit in der provinz Sizilien. *ZPE.* 113: 109-128. At 115-117

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